

Self-Assessment Tool

CHPM2030 Deliverable D5.3

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CHPM2030 DELIVERABLE D5.3

SELF-ASSESSMENT TOOL

Summary:

This document serves as a user guide for the installation and work-flow of the CHPM Self-Assessment Tool. This tool is based on a system dynamics approach and uses the free software Vensim Model Reader. The CHPM Self-Assessment Tool allows to simulate revenue stream from both energy and metal extraction levels, and shows how it is influenced by costs, taxes, metal market, economic growth and other aspects. Users can modify values and compare graph outputs of different scenarios.

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List of abbreviations

CapEx – capital expenditures
 CHPM SAT – CHPM Self-Assessment Toll
 CREST – Cost of Renewable Energy Spreadsheet Tool
 Dmnl – Dimensionless
 EGS – enhanced geothermal system
 GETEM – Geothermal Electric Technology Model
 Inc. – incorporation – suffix indicating corporation
 LEAP – Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning system
 LCOE – levelized cost of energy / levelized cost of electricity
 LLC – Limited liability company
 NREL – National Renewable Energy Laboratory
 OpenEI – Open Energy Information
 OpEx – operational expenditures
 SAM – System Advisor Model
 SD – System Dynamics
 TED – Technology and Environmental Database
 U.S. DOE – The United States Department of Energy
 USD – U.S. dollars

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and role of Task 5.3

A self-assessment tool based on system dynamic approach (e.g. Forrester 1961) was developed within the Task 5.3 Decision support for economic feasibility assessment. The CHPM Self-Assessment Tool can be run only in Vensim Model Reader (Ventana System, Inc. 2015) which allows users to assess feasibility of different CHPM scenarios according their own datasets. The CHPM Self-Assessment Tool itself and CHPM default scenario can be downloaded from MinPol website (<http://www.minpol.com/references.html>)

1.2 CHPM Self-Assessment Tool (CHPM SAT)

The Self-Assessment Tool is based on System Dynamics. This tool can investigate and model complex dynamic problems in terms of stocks (the accumulation of things), flows (the motion of things) and feedback loops at any level of aggregation.

Default values (to be modified by user based on their own dataset) are based on data gathered in D5.2 as well as critical parameters provided by previous WPs. Also, external sources (e.g. Mines and Nathawani 2013, Neupane and Wendt 2017, OpenEI 2016, Robinson 2015), derivation from other operational EGS power plants or theoretical models for metal extraction plants (described in D5.2) were used for specific default values (e.g. overall CapEx and OpEx of future CHPM plant).

1.2.1 System Dynamics background

The field of System Dynamics was first developed by J. Forrester in his book “Industrial Dynamics” (Forrester, 1961). It was applicable for a wide range of applications ranging from management of research and development, urban stagnation and decay, commodity cycles, and the dynamics of growth in a finite world. Because of its broad scope, its name has been changed to System Dynamics.

Important current simulation environments include Vensim (Ventana Systems Inc., www.vensim.com), STELLA and iThink (isee Systems, <http://www.iseesystems.com>) PowerSim (Powersim Software AS, www.powersim.com), and AnyLogic North America, LLC. (AnyLogic, www.anylogic.com).

1.2.2 Vensim modelling environment

Vensim has a graphical modelling environment which allows the user to insert all the system dynamics elements and conceptualize, document, simulate, analyse, and optimize models of dynamic systems (Ventana System, Inc. 2015). The main elements are: Variables (default representation is a borderless text); Levels (default representation is a box with text); Arrows which connect variables and

Fig. 1: Vensim software environment

levels to each other forming causal links; Rates (double line arrows) which regulate the flow into and out of a level variable. All these elements can be manipulated using an equation editor and the other functions within Vensim are for setting up the model, several user interface options and displaying results of simulations.

1.3 Other presently used economic models

Beside the CHPM Self-Assessment, the D5.3 also present an overview other of presently used economic models.

Long-range Energy Alternatives Planning system (LEAP): LEAP is a software tool which is used for energy policy analysis and climate change mitigation assessment which was developed at the Stockholm Environment Institute (Fig. 2, Heap 2012). It is a scenario-based modelling tool which can be used to track energy consumption, production and resource extraction from all sectors of an economy. The power of LEAP is from its flexibility to include all types of energy (conventional and renewable) and its built-in capabilities to model climate change assessment with the use of its Technology and Environmental Database (TED). TED describes the technical characteristics, costs and environmental loadings of a range of energy technologies. Many studies (Emodi et al.2017, Nojedehi et al. 2016, Kuldna et al. 2015) which used LEAP took advantage of TED to deliver articles on lowering the environmental impact of future energy systems (as is one of the LEAP objective).

The main “Analysis View” is a hierarchical tree which displays the main data structure for the analysis. It allows the user to create data structures and scenarios and to enter all the data describing both historical data as well as forward-looking scenarios. In the analysis view, the flow of energy resources (extraction to consumption) starts from bottom and works its way to the top. This can be seen from the resources tab and the demand tab. The view (Fig. 2) shows the basic data structure for

Fig. 2: LEAP analysis view

an energy system in an economy which involves consumption (demand), production (transformation) and raw materials (resources).

Geothermal Electricity Technology Evaluation Model (GETEM): GETEM is an excel based tool (Fig. 4) developed by National Renewable Energy Laboratory, U.S. Department of Energy (U.S. Department of Energy 2017). It is used to estimate the Levelized Cost of Electricity for definable geothermal scenarios (Geothermal Electricity Technology Evaluation Model). The tool can be downloaded from their website (U.S. DOE, <https://www.energy.gov/eere/geothermal/geothermal-electricity-technology-evaluation-model>).

The most updated version of the tool is still in the beta phase of testing and has not been rigorously checked or validated (disclaimer in the excel file). This tool, as the name suggests, is geothermal specific and, as such, cannot be used for other energy systems (compared to other tools).

Fig. 3: Scenario editor in GETEM.

The tool is very detailed for geothermal systems and has default values for most of the parameters (in case we do not have data) and is focused on the economic analysis of the geothermal facility. The scheduling tab divides the project into various stages ranging from exploration to plant construction and start-up. This tool was used to analyse the risk for the Geothermal Technology Program of the U.S. Department of Energy (McVeigh et al., 2007)

Cost of Renewable Energy Spreadsheet Tool (CREST): CREST is another excel tool developed by National Renewable Energy Laboratory, U.S. DOE (Fig. 5, NREL 2011). It is a cash flow model which can allow policy and decision makers to assess economic viability, design incentives and impact of renewable energy systems from an economy point of view. The tool is available for different renewable projects including geothermal energy as separate excel files and is available from the website of NREL (NREL, <https://financere.nrel.gov/finance/content/crest-cost-energy-models>).

Unlike GETEM tool which distinguishes between a hydrothermal reservoir and EGS reservoir, CREST does not make any such distinction. It is intended for researchers who want quick preliminary results without going too much into the details of the project.

Performance, Cost, Operating, Tax & Financing Inputs					
Check		Units	Input Value	Notes	
Project Size and Performance					
	Generator Gross Nameplate Capacity	MW	15	?	
	Net Capacity Factor, Yr 1	%	85.5%	?	
	Production, Yr 1	kWh	1123,47,000	?	
	Select Production Degradation Level of Detail		Annual	?	
	Annual Plant Production Degradation	%	0.5%	?	
	Ratio of Plant Capacity to Thermal Potential	ratio	0.95	?	
	Thermal Resource Potential, Yr 1 (kW-electric equivalent)	MW	15.8	?	
	Select Thermal Resource Degradation Level of Detail		Annual	?	
	Annual Degradation of Thermal Resource	%	3.0%	?	
	Project Useful Life	years	25	?	
Cost Level of Detail: Confirmation and Site Development Costs					
	Select Cost Level of Detail		Intermediate	?	
Exploration Costs Attributed to Project					
	Total Exploration Costs (before time-value of investment)	\$/kW	\$175	?	
	Exploration Well Drilling Success Rate	%	50%	?	
	Number of Successful Exploration Wells Required	#	1	?	
	Avg cost per exploration well	\$/Well	\$40,00,000	?	
	Non-well exploration costs	\$	\$7,50,000	?	
	Exploration Cost, before time-value of investment (for reference)	\$/kW	583	?	
	Expected Return on Exploration Capital (from investment to COD)	%	100%	?	
Cost-Based Tariff Rate Structure					
	Payment Duration for Cost-Based Tariff	years	20	?	
	% of Year-One Tariff Rate Escalated	%	0.0%	?	
	Cost-Based Tariff Escalation Rate	%	0.0%	?	
Forecasted Market Value of Production; applies after Incentive Expiration					
	Select Market Value Forecast Methodology		Year One	?	
	Value of energy, capacity & RECs, Yr 1	¢/kWh	4.00	?	
	Market Value Escalation Rate	%	2.0%	?	
Operations & Maintenance					
	Select Cost Level of Detail		Intermediate	?	
Operations & Maintenance:					
	O&M Cost Inflation, initial period	%	2.0%	?	
	Initial Period ends last day of:	year	10	?	
	O&M Cost Inflation, thereafter	%	2.0%	?	
	Field				
	Fixed O&M Expense, Yr 1	\$/kW-yr	\$2.00	?	
	Variable O&M Expense, Yr 1	¢/kWh	1.00	?	
	Plant				
	Fixed O&M Expense, Yr 1	\$/kW-yr	\$2.00	?	
	Variable O&M Expense, Yr 1	¢/kWh	2.00	?	
	Other O&M				
	Insurance, Yr 1 (% of Total Cost)	%	0.4%	?	

Fig. 4: Input page in CREST.

System Advisor Model (SAM): SAM is a performance and financial model developed by National Renewable Energy Laboratory, U.S. Department of Energy (Fig. 6, NREL 2010). It is designed to facilitate decision and policy makers who are involved in the renewable energy industry. Unlike the other models, SAM is more detailed and require more inputs from the user side to generate results. The other models could be used to generate preliminary results and accordingly researchers can use SAM tool to perform more detailed analysis. The tool supports a variety of renewable energy projects including geothermal projects.

Fig. 5: The SAM main window showing monthly electricity generation and the annual cash flow

2 Installation of the Vensim Model Reader

The CHPM Self-Assessment Tool (CHPM_Self_Assessment_Tool.vmf) was developed in Vensim software (Ventana System, Inc. 2015) and user can run own simulations via freely distributed Vensim Model Reader. This file together with a default scenario file (CHPM-default.vdf) are an integral parts of the Deliverable D5.3 and the both files can be downloaded from MINPOL website: <http://www.minpol.com/references.html>.

The Vensim Model Reader software can be downloaded from official Vensim website, from the Free Downloads subpage (Fig. 6, URL: <https://vensim.com/free-download/>).

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2. Return to the McGraw-Hill Business Dynamics page (if you came from there!)

Current version: 7.3

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- The Vensim Model Reader may be distributed for free with your models (including commercial use).
- When you're done downloading, check out our new getting-started videos, Building a Simple Vensim Model and Running models with Vensim PLE and the Model Reader.**
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 - You entered your email address incorrectly.
 - It was delivered, but is in your spam/bulk email folder.
 - Our emails are being blocked by your servers. You will need to contact your IT administrator or ISP to fix this, we cannot help.
 - You did not tick the box below titled "please tick this box".
 - Browser issues. Try a different browser.
- If you have problems, start by checking the FAQ (there is a link to this at the top of the page). If the FAQ does not help, click the "Contact us" link at the top of this page, there is a section titled "If you need help or technical support", follow the instructions for PLE users.

Choose a Product and Platform:

Anti-spam Please tick this box

Product Vensim PLE Model Reader

Platform Windows (XP/Vista/7/8/8.1/10) Macintosh OSX (10.9+)

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Name USER NAME

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- Support
- The Workbench
- Vensim Model Reader
- Vensim online course – advanced version
- Vensim online course – basic version
- Vensim online course –

Fig. 6: Free Downloads subpage at the Vensim software webpage

Vensim Model Reader may be distributed for free together with the CHPM Self-Assessment Tool file for both personal and commercial use. For downloading the Model Reader from the Vensim website page, you need to tick anti-spam tick-box, select Model Reader (Vensim PLE is a licence for education or research purposes), Windows/Macintosh and type your name and email address (two-times for confirmation) at the Free Downloads subpage. In the last step on this subpage, press the blue “Download software” button and following screen (Fig. 7) will inform you, that instruction on how to download Vensim will be emailed to your email box.

Thank you. Instructions on how to download Vensim have been emailed to you.

Common problems.

This system is automated. If you do not receive an email, it's probably due to one of the following reasons.

1. You entered your email address incorrectly.
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PLEASE NOTE : Currently our emails to any @web and @gmx address are being blocked. Please use a different email address if you can.

Vensim download center v1.0.

Fig. 7: Confirmation screen about sending the downloading instruction

Check the email box, in some cases also spam/bulk folder for an email from address noreply@vensim.com and subject: Vensim download instruction. The URL will navigate you to downloading the Model Reader (VensimREDx32Setup). After successful download, run the application by double-click.

Fig. 8: Installation of the Vensim Model Reader

3 Work with CHPM Self-Assessment Tool in the Vensim Model Reader

The CHPM SAT can be open by double click on the file CHPM_Self_Assessment_Tool.vmf or user can launch the Vensim Model Reader and open CHPM SAT via File > Open model... > folder of CHPM_Self_Assessment_Tool.vmf (Fig. 9). As a second step, look on the View dropdown menu and use ideally *Zoom 100%* for the best display of the model.

User can notice several toolbars:

1. Down-left you can change „views“ in dropdown menu – in our case there are two system dynamic models („CHPM Plant“ and „Metal Market“) and „CHPM Self-Assessment Tool“.

Fig. 9: Software environment of the Vensim Model Reader

2. Tools for outputs analyses – user can view e.g. “causes tree”, graphs or tables of individual variables by click on the variable and then select intended tool.
3. In the horizontal toolbar users can create and simulate their own CHPM scenarios. The CHPM SAT is set on default values (CHPM-default), which can be run by pressing the “SimSetup” button. You can modify the scenario by typing a different scenario name into “Simulation results file name” and then press the SyntheSim button. This allow you to modify values in the CHPM SAT output view and also directly in both system dynamic models. Values can be changed by typing the exact values, use a scroll-bar (Fig. 10) or, in special cases, by clicking on the text in pale blue rectangle and set input (X axe, time in years), output (Y axe values of the variable for the interval). For example, “Flow rate“ will be 70 L/s in year 0 and is continually decreasing to 50 L/s in year 30 (Fig. 11).

- c) Cost/Revenue – this panel serves for modification of expenditures, electricity price and taxations. Values which are in percentages (%) are displayed as 0 (0%) to 1 (100%). For example, in the case of 10% royalty for metal extraction, user have to set value on 0.1.
- d) Metal Market – panel for modification of values which are creating metal market, such as metal demand, economic growth, metal price etc.
- e) External Influences – user can modify specific variables which are influencing metal market and so also the revenue stream from the CHPM plant.

Fig. 13: CHPM SAT Values modification menu

2. Graph outputs are showing results from scenario(s) simulation based on values which were set in the *Values modification menu*. Also graphs are grouped into several panels:

Traditional Mining

Recycling Chain

Revenue flows (USD)

Metal Market

CHPM Production Details

URL for the CHPM Self-Assessment Tool and CHPM-default scenario download:
<http://www.minpol.com/references.html>

4 Annex

4.1 CHPM Plant – Screenshot from Vensim Model Reader

4.2 Metal Market – Screenshot from Vensim Model Reader

You can also learn about software environment and workflow via official Vensim short video tutorial: ["https://vensim.com/running-models-with-vensim-ple-and-the-model-reader/"](https://vensim.com/running-models-with-vensim-ple-and-the-model-reader/)

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